

SPEECH ACTIVITY AND ITS TYPES.

Boymatova Aziza

Termiz State University, Faculty of Foreign Philology,
Philology and Language Teaching (English)
student of group 422

Abstract: When students get poor marks on writing assignments, it is often because they don't have a solid grasp of the parts of speech and how they function. Parts of speech is a topic that needs to be revisited regularly in order for it to stick, but maybe you're a busy teacher who doesn't have time to rework every activity you know! This article provides information on the correct analysis and study of speech activity in foreign languages.

Key words: speech ability, pedagogical skill, active speech, passive speech, pedagogical requirements, speech imitation.

Communication is important in the process of people communicating with each other. One of the tools directly refer to language and speech activity. Speech is human is the highest and main means of activity. Because man is different from other creatures. It is also speech that separates. Expression and exchange of speech process, language as a special kind of language activity is specific form of living. Speech is its oral and written expression the processes of being, that is, the process of speaking and its result are understood. Speech activity is the communication process itself, the concept of speech activity is, on the one hand, language exchange and formation of ideas using tools, on the other hand, interrelated, including the perception and understanding of language structures describes a process consisting of actions. The following types of speech activity are distinguished: active speech and passive speech. The speaker's speech is active speech, the listener's speech is passive speech. Of course, both types of speech are important in communication takes its place. If we consider the problem of when speech appeared in man, in man it is possible to single out a number of ideas that had a significant impact on the emergence of this mental phenomenon. Here, the starting point is work, or rather, activity is a joint form, as a result of which there is an urgent need for communication will be. Not to worry: here are of speech activities, grammar games, and creative lessons to help students of all ages learn this tough topic once and for all!

All you need are some ping pong balls and some plastic cups. Label the cups with the parts of speech and write vocabulary words on the ping pong balls. Have students toss the words into their corresponding parts of speech. You can have students guess which part of speech will fill up first, or challenge them to fill all the cups as quickly as they can! For this listening game, say, "raise your hands when you hear a verb" before you start reading. This activity will allow students to practice parts of speech as well as listening carefully. Arrange your students in a circle, or a few small group circles of 4-5 students each, and give them a ball. Give each group a part of speech and instruct them to say a word that corresponds with that part of speech whenever they have the ball. After they say their word aloud, they roll the ball to someone else in the circle. This is a great activity for young students who are learning basic vocabulary and developing hand-eye coordination.

Acquiring pedagogical skills, education for teachers not only being the ground that ensures its effectiveness, but at the same time its it also increases its prestige in the society, and respect for students arises will come. Organization of practical actions to improve professional skills is pedagogical to avoid mistakes made or being made in the activity, students, achieve success in relationships with colleagues and parents creates an opportunity. Among all professions, the teaching profession is special and important acquires social importance. After all, the teacher is the perfection of the consciousness of the future generation the foundation is a person who educates young people. Today it is young people nature, society, social life, thinking, ideologically-politically refined teaches the laws of development, prepares young people for work, helps them master professional secrets and is important for society solves social and economic situations. This is the responsibility of the teacher to become a skilled master of his profession, having an educational effect on students, and their interests, abilities, talents, beliefs and practical skills in every way it requires to be the owner of a profession that looks for ways of development. for this to constantly improve students' professional skills, skills and qualifications, to take care of them in every way, to create the necessary conditions material and spiritual - methodical and technical support, teachers it should help to regularly increase creative initiative.

According to its vital meaning, speech has many functional properties. This not only a means of communication, but also a means of thinking, consciousness, memory,

information (written texts) carrier, managing other people's behavior and the person's own is a means of regulating behavior. Due to its many functions, speech is a polymorphic activity, i.e. in different forms for different functional purposes presented: external, internal, monologue, dialogue, written, oral, etc. Speak up although these forms are related to each other, their vital purpose is not the same. For example, external speech mainly plays the role of a means of communication, internal - a means of thinking. Written speech often works as a way of memorizing information. A monologue bilateral, and dialogue serves the process of two-way information exchange. It is important to distinguish language from speech. Their main differences are as follows. Language is a customary system of symbols, with the help of which people have a certain meaning and meaning a combination of sounds is transmitted. On the other hand, speech is writing has the same meaning and the same meaning as the corresponding system of symbols is a set of pronounced or perceived sounds. Language uses it speech is the same for all people. This is the speech of the speech the psychology of a person or a group of people with unique characteristics represents, the language is for itself people and not only living people, but reflects the psychology of all people who lived. before and in this language was talking.

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